

Particulate Matter, SO₂ and NO₂ Monitoring of Nandurbar City, Maharashtra India

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ABSTRACT

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of the Particulate Matter, SO₂ and NO₂ Monitoring of Nandurbar city, Maharashtra, India from April 2023 to March 2024. The findings indicate that the concentration of SPM and PM₁₀ exceeds the permissible limits established by the National Ambient Air Quality Standards (NAAQS). A notable spike in SPM and PM₁₀ levels was recorded the months of January, February, March, April, September, October, November, and December. In the months of March and April, SPM and PM₁₀ crosses the permissible limits at the beginning of Summer due to more wind flow. At the beginning of the winter months of September, and October, and in the festival of light month of November, December SPM and PM₁₀ is too high. In contrast, the levels of sulfur dioxide (SO₂) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) remain within the NAAQS guidelines only SO₂ was high in the month of April. Sampling was conducted continuously for two days a week at intervals of approximately four hours for SO₂ and NO₂, and eight hours for PM₁₀, totaling a 48-hour monitoring period. The findings are based on an eight-hour continuous air sampling conducted at each of the three designated sites within Nandurbar city.

Keywords: Ambient air quality, particulate matter, NAAQS, Sulphur dioxide, Nitrogen Dioxide

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution is a complex issue in many Indian cities, resulting from several sources, including vehicle emissions, solid waste buildup on roads, industrial gas emissions, construction site debris, waste incineration, and seasonal factors like burning agricultural residues, dust storms, and sea salt. Significant environmental problems are caused by the fastest rate of urbanization, which is made worse by the expansion of industries, population, and vehicles [1]. The rapid economic development accompanying this urban expansion is resulting in severe air quality concerns in many urban areas across India [2]. Furthermore, air pollution is increasingly recognized as a threat to public health in numerous developing nations. It is essential to assess current air quality levels and adopt a scientific approach to understanding both outdoor and indoor air pollution, as well as their health implications [3]. The inhalation of contaminated air can lead to significant health repercussions, particularly in urban settings where

pollution levels frequently exceed safe limits [4]. Air pollution is a serious regional and global issue that impacts the economy, society, tourism, and health [5]. Also, Climate change is predicted to increase the frequency of extreme weather events, which can exacerbate air pollution levels and respiratory complications. [6]. The carcinogenic risk is associated with children due to outdoor and indoor air pollution [7]. The continuous infrastructural and economic development exerted pressure on the environmental conditions of the North Maharashtra Region. In the North Maharashtra region, Nandurbar is a city that has recently been urbanized and is developing an industrial zone also [8]. This article provides information about the pollution status of Nandurbar City, this study is specially carried out on the recommendation of Maharashtra Pollution Control Board, Mumbai. No literature is available so far for the study of the pollution status of Nandurbar City, so this study is crucial for knowing the pollution status of Nandurbar City to society.

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Ambient air quality monitoring was conducted at three distinct sites within Nandurbar city from April 1st, 2023, to March 31st, 2024. The assessment included parameters such as Respirable Suspended Particulate Matter (RSPM), specifically PM10 (particulate matter with a diameter of 10 μm or less) and PM2.5 (particulate matter with a diameter of 2.5 μm or less), as well as Suspended Particulate Matter (SPM) larger than 10 μm , which were measured using gravimetric methods [9-11]. Additionally, the concentrations of gases present in the air, including Sulphur Dioxide (SO₂) and Nitrogen Dioxide (NO₂), were determined using an air gas sampling machine. Continuous air sampling for RSPM was performed over eight hours, while gas samples were collected over four hours at each location [12-15].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Narration of study Area

Nandurbar city is located in the northwest corner of Maharashtra state, India, in the Khandesh region: Coordinates: 21.37°N 74.25°E, Elevation: 210 meters (688 feet). It is situated at near the border of Gujarat state to the northwest, Madhya Pradesh to the east, Dhule district to the southeast, and Nashik district Nandurbar city is located in the northwest corner of Maharashtra state, India, in the Khandesh region. Nandurbar is a hilly region with a dry climate and tropical temperatures [16]. The following locations are represented in Table-1 that have been shortlisted for Ambient Air Quality Monitoring under NAMP.

Table:1: Locations shortlisted for Air Monitoring Project in Nandurbar City

Sr. No.	Location Finalized	Latitude	Longitude
1.	Maharashtra Oil Extraction, MIDC Nandurbar (Industrial), Station Code: S1	21°22'44" N	74° 15' 28" E
2.	Nandurbar Municipal Corporation, Nandurbar (Commercial), Station Code: S2	21°22'4.8" N	74° 14' 31" E
3.	Dhule Chaufuli, Nandurbar (Residential/ Commercial), Station Code: S3	21°21'43" N	74° 15' 3.6" E

2.2. Sampling methods

2.2.1 Determination of Suspended Particulate Matter (SPM) Respirable Suspended Particulate Matter (RSPM) (PM10):

The cyclonic low technique respirable dust sampler draws in air from the environment at an average flow rate of 1.0 m³ per minute. Due to the action of centrifugal force, larger non-respirable particles are deposited into a cup located at the base of a conical

hopper. Concurrently, particles smaller than 10 μm are allowed to exit through the central opening at the top of the hopper, where they are collected on pre-weighed EPM 2000 filter paper (GF/A 20.3 cm x 25.4 cm). The final concentration of PM10 is determined by calculating the difference in weight of the filter paper before and after sampling, which is then divided by the total volume of air sampled. The resulting PM10 concentration is expressed in micrograms per cubic meter ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$).

Fig:1 The annual average concentrations of Suspensible Particulate Matter (PM10) analyzed at all locations S1, S2 and S3.

Fig:2 The annual average concentrations of Respirable Suspensible Particulate Matter (PM10) analysed at all locations S1, S2 and S3.

2.2.2 Sampling and analysis of gaseous pollutants (SO₂ and NO₂):

For the analysis of SO₂, the Modified West & Gaeke Method was employed to collect samples from the ambient air. This method utilizes an air bubbling technique, allowing SO₂ to be absorbed in a 0.04 M tetrachloromercurate solution, forming a

dichlorosulphitomercurate complex at a flow rate of 1 L/min. The addition of 0.6% sulphamic acid, 0.2% formaldehyde, and para rosaniline solution facilitates the conversion of this complex into a highly colored pararosanilinemethylsulphonic acid. The specific absorbance of this compound is measured at 560 nm. For NO₂ sampling, the Modified Jacobs & Hochheiser method was utilized, where the gas is

absorbed in a solution of sodium hydroxide and sodium arsenite. A pipetted aliquot of the collected sample is treated with hydrogen peroxide, sulphanimide, and NEDA, followed by a color development period, after which the absorbance of the solution is measured at 540 nm [17-18]. Samples were collected using a 1% potassium iodide solution

in a 0.1 m phosphate buffer. This phosphate buffer comprises potassium dihydrogen phosphate (KH₂PO₄), disodium hydrogen phosphate (Na₂HPO₄), and potassium iodide. Following the collection of samples, the absorbance was measured at a wavelength of 352 nm using a UV spectrophotometer (Lambda-25).

Fig.3. The annual average concentrations of SO₂ analysed at all locations S1, S2 and S3.

Fig.4. The annual average concentrations of NO_x analysed at all locations S1, S2 and S3.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the present study, measured the concentration of PM₁₀, SO₂ and NO₂ in terms of microgram per cubic meter, at selected locations in Nandvariationsurbar

city. These are as Maharashtra Oil Extraction (Industrial) Nandurbar, Latitude 21.3811680 and Longitude 74.259130. Municipal Corporation Building (Commercial) Latitude 21.3690380 and Longitude 74.2429040, Nandurbar and Dhule Chafuli (Residential), Nandurbar. The period was from 1st April 2023 to 31st March 2024. Monthly variation of monitored pollutants in the study location are graphically represented in Figure 1 to Figure 4.

Suspended Particulate Matters: SPM:

At outcomes, SPM extended from 48 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to 148 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, 147 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to 360 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to 300 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ at S1, S2, and S3 respectively as shown in Fig.1. The SPM concentration is least at S1 while SPM concentration is high at S2 and S3. S1 crosses the permissible limits of SPM only in the month of April. S2 and S3 cross the permissible limits in the months of January, February, March, April, September, October, November, and December. In the months of March and April, SPM crosses the permissible limits at the beginning of Summer due to more wind flow. At the beginning of the winter months of September, and October, and in the festival of light month of November, December SPM is too high.

Respirable Suspended Particulate Matters: RSPM (PM10):

At outcomes, PM10 extended from 80 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to 400 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, 125 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to 240 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, 40 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ to 410 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ at S1, S2 and S3 respectively as shown in Fig.2. S1, S2 and S3 cross the permissible limits in the months of January, February, March, April, September, October, November, and December. In the months of March and April, PM10 crosses the permissible limits at the beginning of Summer due to more wind flow. At the beginning of the winter months of September, and October, and in the festival of light month of November, December PM 10 is too high.

Gaseous Pollutants (SO₂, NO₂): This study evidenced, that the concentration of

SO₂ ranged 2.5 to 7.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, 3.8 to 5.9 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, 2.3 to 5.9 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, at locations S1, S2 and S3 respectively and it is evidenced, that the level of SO₂ at all location are

well below the maximum permitted limit given National Ambient Air Quality Standards. however, the high level (7.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) of SO₂ were found in the month of April 2023 at Maharashtra oil extraction Nandurbar MIDC (S1). The most common air pollutant of NO₂ pollutant discussed as further. The entire assessment of NO₂ varied from 7.0 to 12.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, 8.0 to 18.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, 3.5 to 13.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ at locations S1, S2, and S3 respectively.

CONCLUSION:

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of the ambient air quality in Nandurbar city from April 2023 to March 2024. The findings indicate that the concentration of SPM and PM10 exceeds the permissible limits established by the National Ambient Air Quality Standards (NAAQS). A notable spike in SPM and PM10 levels was recorded the months of January, February, March, April, September, October, November, and December. In the months of March and April, SPM and PM 10 crosses the permissible limits at the beginning of Summer due to more wind flow. At the beginning of the winter months of September, and October, and in the festival of light month of November, December SPM and PM 10 is too high. In contrast, the levels of sulfur dioxide (SO₂) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) remain within the NAAQS guidelines only SO₂ was high in the month of April. The primary contributors to air pollution are linked to transportation, although the increase in civil construction activities also generates particulate matter. The significant rise in both the volume and number of vehicles, coupled with inefficient traffic flow, diverse driving patterns, the prevalence of older and less efficient cars, and human interventions necessitate urgent attention.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

We are very much thankful to Maharashtra Pollution Control Board, Mumbai, Sub Regional Office Nashik for funds and Principal, Prof. M. J. Raghuvanshi, Nandurbar Taluka Vidhayak Samiti's, G. T. Patil Art's, Commerce and Science College, Nandurbar for providing necessary facilities

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HOW TO CITE: Manohar Patil, Subhash Khairnar, Ganesh Bagul, Himmat Patil, Tushar Borane, Yogesh Marathe, Kalpesh Patil, V. S. Shrivastava*, Particulate Matter, SO₂ and NO₂ Monitoring of Nandurbar City, Maharashtra India, *Int. J. Sci. R. Tech.*, 2025, 2 (6), 214-220. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15589692>